

DEVELOPMENT OF SMART PACKAGING SENSORS USING ARDUINO STARTER KIT

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Abstract: *The need for product packaging and storage appeared even before ancient times. To be transported from its manufacturer, the goods had to be protected in some way. The more efficient and secure the packaging, the further and safer the product could travel. Today, with the help of good packaging and transport, goods can arrive from one end of the world to the other. In order to achieve all this, the most modern technologies are used for that purpose. They are very popular and so-called smart packaging. These modern packaging are able to show the condition of the goods packed in them, as well as whether it is necessary to put the packaging in a colder or warmer space. Today, with technology development, the possibilities of packaging have expanded many times over. Smart packaging is already used for certain products, and in the near future, it will become something standard related to every package. This paper shows how to create a device using electronic components integrated into the transport packaging to measure different conditions. This device aims to show the amount of light or heat to which the packaging is exposed and to warn if these parameters do not comply with the prescribed ones. The test device used in this paper was constructed using an Arduino Uno board, a temperature and light sensor, an LED diode, and additional electronic components. The program codes with which the device works are written in Arduino IDE software, an open-source editor. The language used for the codes is based on the Python programming language. This paper showed only a small part of how smart packaging could use the Arduino environment in the future. The device tested in this paper can be used most efficiently on transport packaging due to its size. Its main application is to*

detect the conditions around the packaging, process them, and then send the data or warning to the person in charge of product safety.

Keywords: smart packaging, Arduino, sensors, transport, development

1 INTRODUCTION

Packaging means wrapping or bottling products to protect them from damage during transportation and storage (Your Article Library, 2019). The necessity of packaging increases to protect the goods from spoilage and damage, for easier handling and transport. The packaging must be functional, and practical to handle, and easy to use. The consumption of packaging materials mainly determines the price of packaging. That is why it is essential that it economically picks the dimensions of the packaging and chooses the most suitable material for packaging production (Industrija-, 2016).

Smart packaging is a modern form of packaging with a specific sensor or indicator that shows customer information about the condition of the goods packed in the packaging. Smart packaging sensors can be made through various components such as Arduino components (Huff, 2008).

The Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board with a universal serial bus (USB) connecting to a computer (Figure 1). The board has a series of contacts where external electronic components such as motors, relays, light sources, laser diodes, speakers, microphones and many others can be connected. In addition, the board can be powered by a computer via a USB port, a 9V battery, or a separate power source (Mikro knjiga, 2020).

Figure 1: Arduino Uno board (Arduino, 2020)

Arduino boards can be programmed using a set of instructions that are sent to the microcontroller on the board itself. The Arduino programming language and the Arduino software, IDE, are used for these instructions (Arduino, 2020).

The Arduino board is designed as electronics - hardware that can be controlled via open-source code. This has made it possible for various electronics manufacturers to make Arduino-compatible boards. (Mikro knjiga, 2020).

2 MATERIALS

For the needs of developing smart packaging sensors using Arduino components, Arduino board, prototype board, resistors, LED diodes, light and heat sensors, appropriate conductors and micro cables for connection and power supply via USB cable were used.

2. 1 Arduino board

The Arduino Uno comes in the form of a 6.9 x 5.3 cm board programmed via a USB interface. The USB-B connector, located on the board, is used for programming the device and its power supply while connected to a computer. However, suppose the device needs to operate independently of the computer. In that case, it is possible to use a special connector (2.1 x 5.5 mm) as a power source, through which an external power supply with a voltage of 5-12 V is connected. A standard PP3 battery is often used for power. of 9V, for which it is necessary to obtain a suitable adapter. If the device is powered via a USB port, the maximum electrical current that can be counted on is 500 mA. In contrast, in direct power via the connector, the electrical current can go up to 1A (Svet kompjutera, 2018).

2. 2 Breadboard

These boards have simplified the design and testing of simple hardware devices. With their appearance, they need to rework printed circuit boards and solder components ceased while the device was still in the construction phase.

All contact openings on the board can be divided into two groups. The first includes connectors located at the edges, and their purpose is to supply power to the components in the central part of the board. The connectors in these two rows are galvanically connected. One row (usually red) is for voltage distribution (+) and the other (typically blue) for grounding (-). Electrical current is supplied to any of the holes in this block from the power source and then distributed to other connectors of that order (Svet kompjutera, 2018).

2. 3 Light sensors

Light sensors are photoelectric devices that convert light energy (photons) into an electrical signal (electrons). The power these passive devices can transform can be in the spectrum's visible, infrared, and ultraviolet parts (AspenCore, 2018).

2. 4 LDR

LDR is made of one unprotected piece of semiconductor material, such as cadmium sulfide, which can change its electrical resistance from a few thousand ohms in the dark to a few hundred ohms when light falls on it. LDR works by creating free electron pairs in the material itself (AspenCore, 2018).

2. 5 Resistor

The resistor is one of the essential components in electronics. It consists of two wire conductors connected by a resistant material, usually applied to a cylindrical-shaped housing. Resistance is expressed in ohms (Ω). The resistor also has power, which is expressed in watts (W).

2. 6 LED diodes

LED (Light Emitting Diodes) are made of a type of light-emitting semiconductor. They combine P-type semiconductors (high concentration of positive carriers - cavities) with N-type semiconductors (high concentration of negative carriers - electrons). Exposure of the P-N junction to a certain voltage will force electrons and holes to recombine at the P-N junction, releasing energy in the form of light in the process.

3 METHODS

3. 1 Assembling and starting the device

This device is made using the Arduino Starter Kit. It shows only a small part of what could be designed and made for packaging in the future, using better and more advanced technologies that already exist or will exist (e.g., nanotechnologies).

In order for the device to work, it needs power. The Arduino board is powered by a 9V battery that attaches to the board itself.

In addition to powering the Arduino board, it was necessary to bring power to the prototype board so that all connected elements could function. This is achieved using conductors.

The row where the conductor is connected thus received power, and it was necessary to attach one end of the light sensor to the same row. The other end of the light sensor was attached to the second row.

After the circuit was formed, the electrical current could be too high for the device itself, so it was necessary to control it. A resistor is used for this. One end of the resistor was connected in the same row as the other end of the sensor, and the other end of the resistor was hooked up to a new, additional row.

From the third row, to close the circuit, a conductor was connected that leads back to the Arduino board, to the GND socket, representing the ground.

Another conductor was attached, so that the values read by the sensors could be displayed on a PC in Arduino software. One end of the additional conductor was in a row where one end of the light sensor and the other in the Arduino board.

An additional small circuit was made for the LED, which indicates that the packaging is affected by the high level of light or temperature. One conductor is connected at one end to the Arduino board. The other end of the conductor is placed in a new row on the prototype board.

A second resistor is placed in the same row to regulate the amount of electrical current flowing through the small circuit. One end of the resistor is placed in the same row as the conductor, and the other in the new row.

One end is placed in this new row - the anode of the LED. The other end - the cathode of the LED is connected in a new row for grounding.

Finally, a conductor is attached between the cathode of the LED and leads back to the Arduino board to the GND pin (Figure 2).

This process composes the device, but it cannot function without the program code.

Figure 2: Arduino device with light sensor

3. 2 Test device software

In order for the device to work, it was necessary to write the appropriate code in the Arduino IDE.

The code first specifies the pin names for the LED and light sensor. Using the codes “const int ledPin = 13;” and “const int ldrPin = A0;” it was explained that pin 13 will be called ledPin, because an LED is attached to it, and A0 will be called ldrPin because of the light sensor (Figure 3). These are constants that will not change. Int represents an integer.

```
sketch_feb18a - light_with_led.ino | Arduino 1.8.9
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
sketch_feb18a light_with_led
//set pin numbers
//const won't change
const int ledPin = 13; //the number of the LED pin
const int ldrPin = A0; //the number of the LDR pin
```

Figure 3: Specifying pin names

The initial program parameters are set in the void setup section (Figure 4). These are the parameters that define the whole program. "Serial.begin (9600);" command sets the speed at which the Arduino sends information. In this case, the Arduino sends 9600 bits per second. In short, this command specifies the rate of repeating the execution of given operations.


```
sketch_feb18a - light_with_led.ino | Arduino 1.8.9
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
[Icons: Checkmark, Run, Upload, Download, Verify]
sketch_feb18a light_with_led
void setup() {
  Serial.begin(9600);
  pinMode(ledPin, OUTPUT); //initialize the LED pin as an output
  pinMode(ldrPin, INPUT); //initialize the LDR pin as an input
}
```

Figure 4: Specifying pin names

Also, in this section, the pin mode is defined. Command “pinMode (ledPin, OUTPUT);” defines the LED pin as the place that will output the feedback and process information that we can read on display, and the command "pinMode (ldrPin, INPUT);" pin of the light sensor as a place that will receive and read information from the environment.

As mentioned earlier, the void loop section serves as the main part of the code (Figure 5). The first thing defined in this section is to read the amount of light falling on the light sensor. This is done using the command "int ldrStatus = analogRead (ldrPin);".


```
sketch_feb18a - light_with_led.ino | Arduino 1.8.9
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
[Icons: Checkmark, Run, Upload, Download, Verify]
sketch_feb18a light_with_led
void loop() {
  int ldrStatus = analogRead(ldrPin); //read the status of the I
  //check if the LDR status is <= 300
  //if it is, the LED is HIGH
}
```

Figure 5: Void Loop section

The light sensor works by sending a value between level 0 and level 1024 to the Arduino board. In the range of possible 5V, this value of the Arduino board

translates into a 10-bit code. Thus, 0 represents complete darkness, while 1024 is the maximum illumination. These numbers can be translated into lux or lumens with the help of additional codes and formulas if the user needs them.

The next thing written in the code is the If Else loop that turns the LED light on or off depending on the amount of light to which the sensor is exposed. The "If (ldrStatus <= 300)" command is used to check whether the amount of light to which the sensor is exposed is less than 300.

In case the situation is like this, the next thing that is defined is that you need to turn on the LED lamp using the command "digitalWrite (ledPin, HIGH);". After that, with the command "Serial.println (" LDR is DARK, LED is ON ");" the user is explained that the amount of light falling on the sensor is too small and that the LED is active because of this (Figure 6).


```
sketch_feb18a - light_with_led.ino | Arduino 1.8.9
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
sketch_feb18a light_with_led
if (ldrStatus <=300) {
    digitalWrite(ledPin, HIGH);           //turn LED on
    Serial.println("LDR is DARK, LED is ON");
}
```

Figure 6: Amount of light less than 300

In case the amount of light to which the light sensor is exposed is more significant than 300 (else), the command "digitalWrite (ledPin, LOW);" deactivates the LED (Figure 7).


```
sketch_feb18a - light_with_led.ino | Arduino 1.8.9
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
Verify
sketch_feb18a light_with_led
else {
    digitalWrite(ledPin, LOW); //turn LED off
    Serial.println("-----");
}
```

Figure 7: Amount of light greater than 300

4 CONCLUSION

This paper showed only a small part of how the Arduino environment could be used in the future. The device tested in this paper can be used most efficiently on transport packaging due to its size. Its main application is to detect the conditions around the packaging, process them, and then send the data or warning to the person in charge of product safety. This paper shows how to give a device notice for inappropriate light conditions, but that is only a tiny part of what such devices could do and display in the future.

More importantly, this work has shown how such devices will become an everyday part of all packaging and that their possibilities are great. With the appropriate programs and codes, they could offer, in addition to the temperature and amount of light, the color of the product, as well as whether the product was previously removed from the packaging without authorization. Furthermore, they could detect and display atmospheric conditions around effects such as earthquakes, fires, and rains. With a few clicks on the phone, we could also get accurate information about how many degrees Celsius our product currently has and where it is in a warehouse.

Computers are becoming smaller and more compact, and soon microcomputers will be installed on primary (product) packaging without any problems. In addition, small microprocessors could tell customers on the phone if the can they approached was damaged and if it had expired.

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